

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE TRAINING OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF PEDAGOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION BASED ON A COMPETENCY APPROACH

Khafizova Umida

Basic doctoral student of Gulistan State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13770628>

INTRODUCTION

Abstract. In this article, there is a scientific discussion about the practical role of the development of inclusive preparation of students based on the approach of performance measures. It covers essential resources about inclusive environments.

Key words: healthy student, inclusive environment, inclusive knowledge, inclusive principles, Eastern thinkers

Decree No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" and "Education for students deemed worthy of special educational needs" In order to ensure the implementation of decisions PQ-4860 of October 13, 2020 on measures to further improve the education system, I will provide insights and suggestions about current issues and problems of inclusive education and their solutions.

The most pressing issue for us psychologists is to get to know each student individually, to conduct a psychological-pedagogical analysis of the education given to students by subject teachers who teach on the basis of orders. I suggest that every subject teacher should teach students with special needs the same way he teaches healthy students. Science teachers and peers should be treated well, and a disabled student should be treated in the same way as a healthy student. And I will make a proposal that education will be provided on the basis of new innovative projects.

The importance of studying the historical traditions, spiritual wealth, scientific heritage and historical-educational experiences of our ancestors, applying their achievements to life and educational work in successfully solving the issue of raising the future generation as a perfect human being is big.

Eastern thinkers left us the legacy of the need to seriously deal with the problems of education of young people in their works.

The basis that ideologically unites all of their thinkers is that they put family and family education at the top of personal education and development. The

main qualities of education, which have not lost their importance even today, are reflected in their works and legacies, such as honesty, truthfulness, purity, and kindness. They emphasized the need to seriously deal with the problems of youth education. Their need to educate students from a young age, to pay attention to their every action, defects and shortcomings, now has a positive effect on the organization of inclusive education.

Eastern thinkers in their works, as teachers and mentors in schools and madrasas, attached great importance to the use of various methods and means of teaching in bringing a person to intellectual maturity, the pedagogical skill of the teacher and mentor-mentor and the most convenient methods of education in practice. They tried to explain the ways to fight.

Avoiding any discrimination in education, ensuring equal relations, the existence of each student's unique characteristics, opportunities, the need to pay serious attention to him, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Imam G 'Azzoli, Yusuf Khos Hajib, A. Avloni's works, and in order to understand their views and use them in our activities, we need to know the essence of inclusive education, which is relevant today.

Inclusive education is a term used to describe the process of teaching students with special needs in mainstream schools. Inclusive (French inclusive-including, Latin include-I conclude, including) or inclusive education is a term used to describe the process of teaching students with special needs in general education (public) schools

Inclusive education is based on the ideology that excludes any discrimination against students, ensures equal treatment of all people, but creates special conditions for students with special educational needs.

Inclusive education is the development process of general education, which implies the availability of education for all in terms of adapting to the different needs of all students, which provides access to education for students with special needs.

Principles of inclusive education:

- the value of a person does not depend on his abilities and achievements;
- everyone has the right to feel and listen;
- all people need each other;
- real education can be carried out only in the conditions of real relationships;
- all people need the support and friendship of their peers;

- all students are more likely to achieve what they are capable of than to fail;

First of all, it is necessary to choose a strong-willed, wise, caring and religious teacher and educator who has mastered the methods of moral and intellectual education. He should be healthy, clean-loving, honest and an educator who can treat people well." Ibn Sina emphasized the teacher's pedagogic skill and responsible duty in teaching students, and before teaching students, the teacher should study their behavior and check their knowledge, interest, and determine what they are capable of. , and then gives such directions to the teacher, thinking that he should recommend him to acquire a trade or science.

One of the most urgent problems is to provide qualified, highly educated teachers to students who are receiving special education. It would be appropriate if every teacher taught a student with special education with love and uplifts his spirit in every lesson, and every lesson was conducted on the basis of modern information technologies. In the inclusive education system, it would be appropriate if the student was given an understanding of the profession and given hours of psychology lessons. I would like to suggest that roundtable discussions should be organized with people who have gained fame and achieved good results as a result of the formation of knowledge and skills based on their chosen fields. With this, a student who has been educated individually feels that he belongs to society. I suggest that special education students should be changed to the lesson schedule. The proposal is that physical education, music, technology, informatics, and fine arts should be introduced.

In the family, it is necessary to give understanding so that parents can support and create conditions for their children and always encourage them. It is necessary to introduce manuals for parents of students in inclusive education. In conclusion, I would like to say that every student with disabilities can live well, and if there are many people who help him and meditate, he will never struggle to find his place in life. In order for them to feel that they are a necessary person in our society, they should be more in the circle of friends who motivate them. We psychologists will have achieved our goal if the above suggestions are implemented. We are proud to have contributed to the delivery of another mature and strong personnel to our society.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni. Ta'lim to'g'risida. 2020 yil 23 sentyabr, O'RQ637-son. (Qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 24.09.2020 y. 03/20/637/1313-son)

2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoevning Oliy Majlisga murojaatnomasi. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057> 29.12.2020 Uchastie roditeley, semi i soobshchestva v inklyuzivnom obrazovanii. Texnicheskiy putevoditel. YuNISEF, 2014.
3. V.Xitryuk va boshqalar. Rabota pedagoga s roditelyami v usloviyax inklyuzivnogo obrazovaniya. Nauchnyy dialog. 2017. № 8. str-426
4. INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNING DOLZARB MASALALARI: MUAMMO VA ULARNING YeChIMLARI mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya MATERIALLARI TO'PLAMI. TOSHKENT - 2021
5. Nogironligi bo'lgan shaxslarning huquqlari to'g'risida. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni. (Qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 15.10.2020 y., 03/20/641/1389- son)

